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Characterization and Analysis of Cracked Hydrocarbon Fractions in Used Lubricating Oil

**N. H. Peter¹, D. A. Idowu^{2,*}, R. E. Ereh³, R. Z. Kabantiyok⁴, A. C. Ikeji⁵,
O. I. Oresgun⁶, I. O. Popoola⁷**

¹ Department of Petroleum Engineering, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

² Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

³ Department of Nuclear Applications, Aachen University of Applied Sciences, Juelich, Germany

⁴ Department of Research and Innovation, Schrödinger Technologies Limited, Kano State, Nigeria

⁵ Department of Laboratory and Medical Pathology, Mayo Clinic, Rochester, Minnesota, USA

⁶ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou, China

⁷ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Lagos State University, Lagos State, Nigeria

*E-mail address: idowudaniel284@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study was aimed at regenerating used lubricating oil into any useful product as well as investigating the cracked hydrocarbons present in it if any. This was based on the fundamental fact that as a result of prolonged usage of the lubricating oil in the crankcase over long distance miles, some cracking must have taken place as well as degradation due to oxidation, as well as contamination thus reducing its viscosity. The methods used to achieve the results were chemical desludging and neutralization, vacuum distillation and gas chromatography. From results obtained, used lubricating oil can be regenerated to base oil, burner fuel though it burns with smoky flame and likely diesel. The light transparent base oil was of appreciable viscosity and comparable to standard. Also, the diesel fraction obtained was distilled at cut temperature range of 260-280 °C while the lube oil fraction was distilled at cut temperature range of 310-330 °C. The two fractions however contained few cracked hydrocarbons. The cracked hydrocarbon in the diesel fraction is decane (C₁₀H₂₂) while the cracked hydrocarbons in the lube oil fraction include n-Hexadecane (C₁₆H₃₄) and n-Heptadecane (C₁₇H₃₆). Therefore, an appreciable part of what we refer to as 'used lubricating oil' can be regenerated and if further work is done by

incorporating additives, can be used again in cars. The masses can do the environment good by going into used lubricating oil regeneration and avoid economic waste as well as environmental pollution.

Keywords: Lubricating oil, Cracked Hydrocarbon, Vacuum Distillation, Gas Chromatography, Environmental Pollution

1. INTRODUCTION

Lubricating oil is largely used in automobiles and marine engines, and other machines. Lube oil has a critical role to reduce friction and to ensure that machines need to be more energy efficient in terms of fuel efficiency and power output. Lube base oil is a term used to describe lubricants made from the gas oil fraction, a byproduct of petroleum processing, which boils between 200-350 °C.

Two types of base oil sources are used in lubricant products: synthetic base oils and mineral oil which are based on fossils with paraffinic, naphthenic, and aromatic characteristics spanning from carbon atoms C₂₀ to C₄₀. Every compound is unique and can be used in a way that best qualify the requirements of the intended climate system. While five different types of chemicals dominate the synthetic oil base market, they include olefin oligomers, particularly polyalphaolefins (PAOs); esters (polyols); alkylated aromatics; Specialty lubricants are hydrocarbons that have been substituted with fluorine, chlorine, or polyether. (Shugarman, 2006).

Synthetic or non-synthetic lubricating oils are petroleum by-products, used for automotive or industrial purposes, which after the indicated period of use recommended by the equipment manufacturers deteriorate in part, forming oxygenated compounds (organic acids and ketones), polynuclear aromatic compounds of high viscosity (and potentially carcinogenic), resins and lacquers. In addition to the basic oil degradation products, there are found in the used oil the additives which have been added in the process of formulating these lubricants and which have not yet been consumed, wear metals of lubricated machines and engines and various contaminants such as water, fuel, dust and other impurities. The lubricating oil used may also contain chemicals which are sometimes unscrupulously added to the oil and its characteristic contaminants. (Silveira et al., 2006; Al-Ghouti, 2009; Santos et al., 2015; Santos et al, 2017).

The presence of polyaromatic heteroatom substances, sulphur, chlorine, and bromine (Trisunaryanti et al., 2008) in used lubricant oil also poses serious problems if one wants to use it as a fuel or any other applications.

Used lube oil becomes unsuitable for its original purpose due to a loss of its original properties and/or the presence of impurities. The use of substandard or used lube oils can result in malfunctioning and damage of engines and machinery. Since petroleum-based lubricating oils are among the most valuable products refined from crude oil, in some regions, used lube oils or other materials have occasionally been deliberately added into lube oil to extend the volume sold (Kulathunga and Mahanama, 2013; Bassbasi et al., 2013).

The chemical composition of used lubricating oil varies widely and depends on the original crude oil, the processes used during refining, the efficiency and type of engine that utilized the oil, products of gasoline or diesel combustion, the additives added to the fuel and to the original oil, and the length of time that the oil remains in the engine.

Lubricating oils are among the few oil derivatives that are not fully consumed during their use. Lube oils are designed to withstand very high service temperatures in the internal combustion engines and resist thermal degradation. Manufacturers of additives and formulators of this type of oil have been working on the development of products with longer life, which tends to reduce the production of waste oils. However, with the increase in additivation and the useful life of the oil, the difficulties in the regeneration process of the basic oil after use increase. On the other hand, if we look at the dangers that used oil can cause to the environment, a solution to the difficulties encountered would be easily justified. In addition, re-refining restores the conditions of the basic lubricating oil, whose quality is as good as or even better than the basics of first refining. The refined oils would return to the market, generating jobs, saving foreign exchange and avoiding the increase in environmental pollution. (Lorenzetti and Rossato, 2010).

Used lubricating oil is a very complex mixture of low and high ($C_{15} - C_{50}$) molecular weight aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons (Linnard and Henton, 1979), additives, metals, and various organic and inorganic compounds. It is a hazardous waste, and its components are not easily degraded. If not disposed of properly, it will affect waterways, and if it is thrown into rivers or beaches, it will definitely endanger the environment and human health (Naima and Liaqid, 2013; Guerin, 2008). Lubricant consumption increases each year due to its importance in various applications. Large volumes of used lubricant oil are considered hazardous wastes. This is because the used oil typically consists of a mixture of un-degradable base oil and additives which have high concentrations of metals, varnish, gums, and other asphaltic compounds. (Permsubscul et al., 2007).

Till now, the use of used lubricating oil has not been maximized. Efforts have been made to deal with this waste, by disposing of it in rubbish dumps or buried in the ground, regenerating it into new lubricating oil and extracting used lubricating oil through the combustion process to be used as fuel oil (Mohammed et al., 2013). It is often either burnt or disposed in an uncontrolled landfill. These measures are unacceptable for the environmental damage it might be bring, since the waste lubricant oils contain numerous additives that are harmful to human health. (Serrano et al., 2003). Some places now have relevant regulations to prevent these very profitable but illegal activities. On the other hand, used lube oil could contain hazardous substances such as gasoline or diesel, additives, and heavy metals (Vazquez-duhalt, 1989; Carusoe, 2014). As a solution, used lubricant could be collected and processed via a re-refining process to become "re-refined lubricating oil" with an equivalent quality to new lubricating oil (Bridjanian and Sattarin, 2006; Emam and Shoaib, 2012; Udonne, 2011) or via direct upgrade from thermal cracking or catalytic cracking.

Reusing used lubricating oil can be done in a few different methods, such as recycling it to make base oil once more or processing it to make fuel energy products. (Alvarracin et al., 2021). For example, when lubricating oil is converted into another type of hydrocarbon product produced is similar in quality to diesel and gasoline products, pyrolysis and catalysis technology can be employed to obtain fuel. Many articles discuss only the process technology without including the characteristics of the feedstock to be refined. Recognizing the physical characteristics of feedstock can be directed to what type of hydrocarbon products will be produced.

Obtaining data on the physical characteristics of feedstock will help us to solve some cases in the operation next. This study aimed at regenerating used lubricating oil into any useful product as well as investigating the cracked hydrocarbons present in it if any.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Materials

The chemicals used for this investigation of used lubricating oil were all analytical grade purity, and the solutions were prepared in distilled water, concentrated tetraoxosulphate(VI) acid (H_2SO_4), toluene and litmus paper.

2. 2. Sample Collection

The used lubricating oil on cars were collected using a container from a roadside mechanic workshop (Hylander Automobiles) located along PTI road, Effumn, Delta State. The samples were labelled and transported to the Department of Petroleum Engineering, Petroleum Training Institute (PTI) laboratory for Analysis.

2. 3. Characterization Analysis

Vacuum distillation unit was used for separating gas oil and residue, the RESTEK 30-meter MXT-1 GC column was used for analyzing cracked hydrocarbons of the used lubricating oil, Viscometer was used to measure the viscosity of the used lubricating oil, Pensky-Martins closed cup equipment was used to determine the flash point of hydrocarbons for quality control.

2. 4. Chemical Desludging and Neutralization

In this process, 166.7 ml (150g) of used lubricating oil and 16.3 ml (30g) of concentrated tetraoxosulphate(VI) acid were mixed in a beaker, in the ratio 5:1; H_2SO_4 acting as the desludging agent. The mixture was then transferred into a magnetic heater-stirrer where it was heated with slow stirring for about an hour (1 hr) to a maximum temperature of 50 °C. The mixture was transferred to a centrifuge. After centrifuging for 45 minutes, a separation into two distinct layers was observed, a mobile oil layer floating on a dense slimy sludge layer at the bottom. The oil top layer was subsequently decanted. Its acidity was tested using a blue litmus paper. It was then neutralized and some quantity of the regenerated oil was poured into a local lamp and tested for burning.

2. 5. Vacuum Distillation

250 ml of the regenerated oil from the desludging process was poured into a two-necked round bottom flask. The connections and joints were properly sealed to avoid leakages. The vacuum pump was started first to depressure the system for about 5 minutes and the heating mantle was switched on. The rise in temperature was carefully monitored as the distillation proceeded at system pressure between 1 to 50 mmHg. The method used was ASTM D1160-87 and after about 50 minutes and at a temperature of 260 °C, the first fraction was collected, a brownish light distillate. The heating proceeded and at about 310 °C, the second fraction, a light transparent distillate was collected. No other fraction came out and heating was discontinued. The whole setup was allowed to cool under vacuum pressure.

2. 6. Gas Chromatography

Using a syringe, 0.5 ml of mix alkane was injected through the injector port into the column as a standard. 0.1 ml of the first fraction of the distillate was then mixed in 0.5 ml of

toluene, toluene acting as the solvent. Thereafter, one of the mixture was injected using a syringe into the column. Similarly, for the second fraction, 0.1 ml of the sample was mixed in 0.5ml toluene while 1 pi of the mixture was injected into the column.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the whole process.

2. 7. Experimental Procedure

From the two fractions obtained from vacuum distillation, the second fraction was tested on the following physical properties to ascertain that it is a base oil; viscosity, viscosity index, flash point and pour point.

2. 8. Determination of the Viscosity

In the viscosity determination, a clean, dry calibrated viscometer was filled with the sample, by applying a slight vacuum to the large-diameter tube and drawing the oil up through the capillary arm, the unit was firmly mounted on the fixture. It was inserted into a temperature bath maintained at 40 °C. Sufficient time was allowed for the charged viscometer to come to the bath temperature and then the head level of oil was adjusted above the first timing by applying slight vacuum. The measurement was made timing the period required for the oil meniscus to flow from the first to second mark. The test was repeated with bath temperature at 100 °C. Thereafter, the viscosity index was calculated.

2. 9. Determination of Pensky-Martins Closed Cup

The second test was performed on flash point, using Pensky-Martins closed cup apparatus. The sample was placed in a brass cup mounted in an air bath which was heated by a gas flame. With agitation of the sample, heat was applied, raising the temperature, until the sample temperature was within 18F of the flash point. A test flame was applied at each 2F increase thereafter, until a flash was observed. Agitation was stopped and the flash point was recorded.

2. 10. Determination of the Pour Point

After, the pour point test was carried out on the sample. The prepared sample was heated above its pour point. The sample was poured into a cylinder and immersed into a cooling medium. Starting at a temperature at least 20F above the expected pour point, the sample was cooled in 5F increments and subsequently observed. When a temperature is reached at which the oil shows no movement as a result of holding the glass sample in a tilted position for 5 seconds, the pour point was recorded.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained from the experiments carried out are summarized in tables below.

Table 1. Comparison between Chromatogram of Mix Alkane Standard and Distilled Fractions.

Mix Alkane Standard			First Fraction		Second Fraction			
Peak	Standard Component	Retention Time (Min)	Peak	Identified Component	Retention Time (Min)	Peak	Identified Component	Retention Time (Min)
1.	C ₁₀ H ₁₂	6.286	1	C ₁₀ H ₁₂	6.414			
2.	C ₂₂ H ₄₆	7.121	2-3	C ₂₂ H ₄₆	6.833-7.242			
3.	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	8.025	4-7	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	7.637-8.549			
4.	C ₁₂ H ₆₆	9.512	8-9	C ₁₂ H ₆₆	9.850-10.140	1	C ₁₂ H ₆₆	10.165
5.	C ₃₂ H ₄₂	11.112	10-11	C ₃₂ H ₄₂	11.177-12.162			
6.	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	12.691	12-15	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	12.145-13.306	2-4	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	10.165
7.	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	13.913	16-17	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	13.678-13.978	5-7	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	13.374-13.994
8.	C ₂₇ H ₅₆	14.436	18-23	C ₂₇ H ₅₆	14.328-15.371	8-9	C ₂₇ H ₅₆	14.357-14.630
9.	C ₁₇ H ₃₀	15.979	24-27	C ₁₇ H ₃₀	15.629-16.384	10-14	C ₁₇ H ₃₀	15.118-15.901
10.	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	17.310	28-33	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	16.726-17.550	15-20	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	16.255-17.543
11.	C ₂₆ H ₃₄	18.587	34-37	C ₂₆ H ₃₄	18.240-19.245	21-24	C ₂₆ H ₃₄	18.105-19.045
12.	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	19.773	38-40	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	19.605-20.128	25-28	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	19.170-19.933
13.	C ₂₉ H ₄₀	20.919				29-32	C ₂₉ H ₄₀	20.210-21.595
14.	C ₂₈ H ₅₈	22.179						
15.	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	23.528						

16.	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	25.089	41-44	C ₂₅ H ₅₂				
17.	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	25.395	45-46	C ₁₅ H ₃₂				

It shows the hydrocarbon component observed as against the peak and retention time. The first fraction which can be regarded now as diesel fraction contains paraffin components within the diesel range as can be seen from Table 1. These include n-Eicosane (C₂₀H₄₂), n-Heneicosane (C₂₁H₄₄), n-Heptadecane (C₁₇H₃₆) and n-Hexadecane (C₁₆H₃₄). However, when compared with the standard diesel range of C₁₃-C₂₅, it will be discovered that there are some overlaps of both higher and tower fractions of paraffinic chains within the fraction, as can be seen from the table, the higher paraffins being dominant than the lower paraffins. Hence the only cracked hydrocarbon chain found in the diesel fraction is decane (C₁₀H₂₂).

However, there are other unidentified components as can be seen from the table, as they showed no retention time at all. This signifies total cracking of such paraffinic components in the fraction. Lu and Kaplan also studied on the difference in chemical composition for unused and used motor oils and to understand their partitioning effect (Lu and Kaplan, 2008). The distribution pattern and profiles of components are, in general, different from virgin to used lube oil and from lube oil to other type of petroleum.

This enables that it is possible to identify oil contamination and to track the oil source. Smaller biomarker compounds including bicyclic sesquiterpanes (BS, C₁₄ to C₁₆) and diamondoid hydrocarbons (C₁₀ to C₁₄ for 17 adamantanes and C₁₄ to C₁₆ for 9 adamantanes) were also investigated. These naturally occurring compounds are thermodynamically stable and resistant to weathering; therefore, they are particularly useful in oil-source correlation and differentiation for those cases where the traditional tri-pentacyclic biomarker terpanes and steranes are absent due to removal during the refining processes. (Yang et al, 2015; Yang et al, 2006; Yang et al, 2009).

Similarly, the second fraction referred to as the lube oil fraction, contain some paraffinic chains of lube oil range such as n-Dotriacontane (C₃₂H₆₆), n-Henicosane (C₂₁H₄₄), n-Hentriacontane (C₃₁H₆₄) and Nonacosane (C₂₉H₆₀). However, when compared to the standard hydrocarbon range in lube oil which is C₂₀-C₃₅, it will be discovered that there are some cracked hydrocarbons found in the chain. These include n-Hexadecane (C₁₆H₃₄) and n-Heptadecane (C₁₇H₃₆). Also, there are some unidentified components as can be seen from the table of the second fraction.

This shows total cracking of such components as they showed no peak no retention time. Moreover, the used lubricating oil, after regenerating, before vacuum distillation was tested in a local lamp to see if it will support complete burning. Though the oil burnt, but with smoky flame. It is apparent that the biomarker abundances and distribution vary greatly in the diesel, the virgin and used lube oils. Petroleum biomarkers were detected to be about 600 µg/g in the lube oils, while only 27.7 and 121 µg/g in the diesel and biodiesel blend. The total biomarkers in the used and the waste lube oils are 378, 599 and 506 µg/g, respectively. The results further disclose that the used and waste lube oils are lube oil-dominated samples (Chun et al., 2015).

As can be seen from table below, two fractions were obtained during the vacuum distillation. The first fraction was obtained at boiling range of 260-280 °C while the second fraction was obtained at boiling range of 310-330 °C. However, due to the fact that the re-distillation was carried out at vacuum temperature, to avoid decomposition or cracking of

products at atmospheric re-distillation, there was need for conversion of vacuum cut-temperatures to atmospheric equivalence as can be seen from the table.

Comparing the atmospheric temperatures of the distilled fractions with standard cut-ranges for petroleum fractions, it will be discovered that the first fraction which was distilled between 371-393 °C could be likened to Automotive Gas Oil (AGO), otherwise known as diesel which has a cut-temperature of 350-400 °C. Similarly, the second fraction distilled at 427-440 °C could be likened to lubricating oil which has a standard cut-range of 400-500 °C. The initial volume used for the re-distillation was 250 ml. The volume distilled for the first fraction was 160ml and the volume distilled for the second fraction was 80 ml. The volume and sum percent can also be seen from the table.

Table 2. Result of Vacuum Re-Distillation of Used Lubricating Oil.

Fraction No.	Cut Temp (°C) Vacuum @ 40 mmHg	Cut Temp (°C) Atmospheric Equivalent	Initial Volume (ml)	Volume Distilled	Volume Percent	Sum Percent
0	IBP-260	IBP-371	250	-	-	-
1	260-280	371-393	250	160	64	64
2	310-330	427-440	250	80	96	32

However, to ascertain that the second fraction was actually, lubricating oil, it was tested on some essential physical properties of lubricating oil and compared to standard as can be seen from table 3. The viscosity index of the regenerated lube oil was 96.8 as against 95 for fresh lube oil. Viscosity is a parameter that influences pollutant emissions. In addition, viscosity will affect the quality required for lubrication because it indicates the fluid's resistance to flow, resulting in degradation. Thus, fuel with a high viscosity value is difficult to flow, causing an unstable fuel supply, which can result in the fuel not burning properly, and reducing engine performance, or causing damage to the fuel system (Li et al., 2001). Diesel fuel with a low viscosity rating may not provide sufficient lubrication to the plunger, barrel, and injector. The viscosity of diesel fuel is usually determined at 40 °C, with the standard for diesel fuel being 2.3 - 6.0 cSt (Samad et al., 2018), thus the resulting DLF viscosity can be used as diesel engine fuel.

The flash point was 239 as against 246 for fresh lube oil while the pour point was -12 as against -12 for fresh lube oil. Hence, the regenerated lubricating oil is comparable to standard. The flash point is the lowest temperature of a substance that produces vapor in sufficient quantities to form a flammable mixture. At this temperature, the vapor pressure reaches a certain limit, so it is flammable.

If the vapor stops burning, if the ignition source is removed again. Flash point is used as one of the descriptive characteristics of liquid fuels but is also used to describe liquids that are not used intentionally as fuel (Arpa and Demirbas, 2009). Fuels with a high flash point are less volatile, while fuels with a low flash point are more volatile.

As a general rule for hydrocarbons, the simpler the molecule, the lower the flash point. Although several equations have been developed to calculate flash points, their usefulness is limited due to significant variations in accuracy. Stirring in the distillation process will cause molecular cracking to break large saturated chains, which produce volatile gases.

Table 3. Compares the chromatogram of mix alkane standard with the two fractions distilled.

	Kinematic Viscosity @ 40 °C	Kinematic Viscosity @ 100 °C	Viscosity Index	Flash Point	Pour Point
Fresh Oil	22-248	185-22	95	246	-12
Regenerated Lube Oil	200	18	96.8	239	-12

4. CONCLUSION

An appreciable part of what we refer to as ‘waste or used lubricating oil’ can be regenerated to diesel fraction, lubricating oil fraction, and burner fuels that can be used in local lamps. The regenerated base oil obtained is comparable to standard and can be used to manufacture any desired lubricating oil such as motor oil. Regenerated base oils contain mostly paraffinic chains with few cracked hydrocarbons present. Therefore, it still maintains the chemical composition of a good lubricating oil which is high paraffinic content. Finally, used lubricating oil should be collected and regenerated into useful fractions rather than discarding them, constituting environmental pollution.

Recommendations

Although the regenerated lubricating oil maintains its physical and chemical properties as fresh lubricating oil, it can be improved upon by incorporating additives and directly tested in car engines. The properties of the diesel fraction can also be tested to determine its workability and the burner fuel can be further treated to get a cleaner burner fuel without smoke. Private sectors can go into the business of recycling and regenerating used lubricating oils.

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